

backcrossing to the Bogor population did not improve nymphal development on the resistant variety (Table 1).

Newly emerged females of any parental or hybrid population placed on IR42 seedlings clearly fell into two discontinuous classes: one that became gravid and survived significantly longer

(17.2 d), and another that quickly died (survived 3.5 d).

Of the NS population, 90% of the females became gravid and survived about 18 d on IR42 seedlings. Most Bogor females died within 5 d. In the hybrid F₁ and F₂ progenies, 5-30% females became gravid with 4-7 d average longevity. Back-

crossing the F₁ hybrid and the NS population increased the parentage of gravid females, but backcrossing with the Bogor population had no such effect (Table 2).

The results indicated that the NS population's ability to infest IR42 is inherited from recessive genes when interbred with avirulent BPH populations. □

Possible genetic isolation between the *Leersia* and rice brown planthopper (BPH)

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It was reported that the *Leersia*-feeding BPH found on *Leersia hexandra* in North Sumatra is morphologically indistinguishable from the rice BPH *Nilaparvata lugens*, but distinctive from each other by their incompatible host requirements. To determine possible genetic barriers, we examined courtship reaction and crossability of the populations.

Courtship reactions were observed by a seedling bridge method. A pre-mating male and a female, 4 to 5 d old, were separately placed at the base of 2 rice seedlings about 10 cm apart in a 17 × 25 cm jar. The leaf blades touched to enable the BPH to communicate by seedling transmitted courtship signals.

When a male and female from the same population were tested, the male moved to the female on the other seedling and they successfully mated. Homogametic matings usually occurred within 4-5 min. Heterogametic matings between the *Leersia*- and rice-BPH seldom occurred except when the male and female met by chance through random wandering.

To confirm our results, mating choice experiments were conducted using a similar method, but three seedlings were set at triangular positions with crossed leaf blades. In one test, a single rice-BPH female was placed on one of the three seedlings and one male each of *Leersia*- and rice-BPH were placed separately on each of the two other seedlings. Only the male rice-BPH reacted and mated with the female within an average 5 min. The male *Leersia*-BPH did not react. In another test, a single male *Leersia*-BPH was allowed to select between *Leersia*- and rice-BPH females. The male always moved to and mated with the female

Leersia-BPH within 4 min. Communication by acoustic courtship signals is not successful between the *Leersia*- and rice-BPH.

Despite failure in courtship communication, *Leersia*- and rice-BPH can mate and produce viable hybrid progeny if confined on the same plant. However, the hybrid progenies were poorly adapted to both host plants. Percentage of adult emergence of the F₁ BPH hybrids were 8-26 on both hosts (see table). The F₂ population also was viable, and survived better than the F₁ on the same host.

We conclude that *Leersia*- and rice-BPH are noninterbreeding sympatric populations. Genetic interchanges between them are greatly restricted by unsuccessful courtship communication, incompatible host plant preference, and breakdown of host affinity in hybrid progenies. □

Adult emergence of the *Leersia*- and rice-BPH, and their F₁ and F₂ hybrids on rice and *L. hexandra*, Jakarta, Indonesia.^a

Cross ^b (♀ × ♂)	Host	No. of adults emerged				% adult emergence
		MF	BF	MM	BM ^c	
L × L	Rice	0	0	0	0	0
	<i>Leersia</i>	0	21	1	24	92
R × R	Rice	0	29	6	12	94
	<i>Leersia</i>	0	0	0	0	0
L × R	Rice	0	7	1	3	22
	<i>Leersia</i>	3	2	0	8	26
R × L	Rice	2	3	3	2	20
	<i>Leersia</i>	1	0	3	0	8
(L × R) ^{2d}	Rice	1	6	3	1	22
	<i>Leersia</i>	10	4	4	1	38
(R × L) ^{2d}	Rice	7	16	9	13	90
	<i>Leersia</i>	9	0	9	0	36

^aFifty first instar nymphs were used for each test. Number of adults emerged was recorded 22 days after introduction of the nymphs. ^bL = *Leersia*-BPH, R = rice - BPH. ^cMF = macropterous female, BF = brachypterous female, MM = macropterous male, BM = brachypterous male. ^dAdults emerged on *L. hexandra* and Pelita I/1 were used, respectively.

Monitoring brown planthopper (BPH) biotypes by rice garden in North Sumatra

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Monitoring BPH biotype nature or virulence is important in variety-oriented BPH management. To monitor BPH biotypes and forecast population surges, we designed a rice garden in which several rice varieties are planted separately in 5- × 5-m plots in a randomized block design.

In Deli Serdang, North Sumatra, in 1983 dry season, we used that technique

to identify local BPH biotypes. Pelita I/1, IR26, IR36, IR42, IR46, IR56, and Bahbolon were transplanted in each plot with three replications on 6 Aug.

BPH infested the plots soon after transplanting. There were bimodal population peaks at 4-5 and 7-8 wk, which corresponded to the maximum nymphal stages of the first and second generations. Between population peaks, brachypterous females emerged. Their population peaked at 6 wk. The BPH population declined sharply after 10 wk, probably because of drought. No hopperburn developed.

However, statistically significant differences in BPH densities were recorded among the rice varieties at six insect development stages. Population was significantly higher on IR42 and the susceptible check Pelita I/1 (see table). Populations were particularly low on IR46, IR56, and Bahbolon. Interestingly,

Comparison of population density of the BPH on 6 different rice varieties at 6 different stages in the rice garden in Deli Serdang, North Sumatra, 1983.^a

Variety	Resistance gene	Insects/hill					
		M-female (2 wk)	F ₁ S-nymph (4 wk)	F ₁ L-nymph (5 wk)	B-female (6 wk)	F ₂ S-nymph (7-8 wk)	F ₂ L-nymph (8-9 wk)
Pelita I/1	None	2.4 ab	252 a	67 a	4.3 a	60 a	6.0 a
IR42	<i>bph 2</i>	3.3 a	202 a	70 a	4.3 a	83 a	7.3 a
IR36	<i>bph 2</i>	1.5 bc	81 b	20 b	0.9 ab	27 b	1.7 b
IR26	<i>Bph 1</i>	1.1 bc	16 bc	7 b	0.4 b	7 bc	0.1 b
IR56	<i>Bph 3</i>	1.3 bc	20 bc	5 b	0.2 b	0.2 c	0.2 b
IR46	<i>Bph 1</i>	1.0 bc	3 c	4 b	0.1 b	0.3 c	0.2 b
Bahbolon	<i>Bph 3</i>	0.4 c	1 c	1 b	0.02 b	0.1 c	0.1 b

^aValues followed by the same letter are not significantly different at 5% level. F₁ = first generation, F₂ = second generation, M-female = macropterous adult female, B-female = brachypterous adult female, S-nymph = 1st- to 3d-instar nymphs, L-nymph = 4th- to 5th-instar nymphs. Time in parentheses indicates weeks after transplanting.

IR26, which had been attacked by BPH biotype 2, showed good resistance. Results indicated that the local BPH population was biotype 3, adapted to IR42, which corresponded with laboratory identification of locally

collected BPH. The rice garden method is recommended as a simple but highly practical method of monitoring BPH biotype shifts, and forecasting BPH population surge and development of other insect pests and diseases. □

Relationship between biochemical characteristics of rice and establishment of yellow stem borer (YSB) larvae

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We conducted greenhouse experiments to determine the ability of YSB larvae to establish themselves on rice accessions with selected biochemical characteristics.

Twenty-day-old seedlings of 6 accessions (see table) and the susceptible check Jaya were transplanted 1/hill in 10-cm earthen pots in a 90- × 60- × 5-cm galvanized iron tray filled with water. Fifty days after seeding, one freshly hatched larva was released on each tiller.

Larval establishment and biochemical characteristics of selected rice accessions, Coimbatore, India.

Accession	Larval establishment (%)	Leaf sheath		Stem		
		Total N (%)	Crude silica (%)	Crude silica (%)	Lignin (mg/g)	Cellulose (mg/g)
W1263	9	3.6	4.8	11.40	417	671
Co 18	20	2.4	2.3	9.87	532	608
IR13641-4	23	5.0	0.6	12.12	279	737
IR13639-39	45	4.9	1.4	5.85	143	887
Sornavazhai	45	3.1	3.7	3.17	583	566
Jaya	50	3.1	1.7	6.51	464	710

Each accession was in 3 replications of 10 hills/replication.

Ten days after larvae were released, single accessions were pulled and the leaf sheath and lumen were carefully observed to determine the presence and position of the larvae. Percent larval establishment was calculated based on larval recovery.

The leaf sheaths and stems of accessions were analyzed for total N, crude silica, lignin, and cellulose.

Larval establishment was lowest in W1263, followed by Co 18 and IR13641-4 (see table). It was highest in susceptible Jaya. Only crude silica content was significantly related to percent larval establishment. The resistant accessions had more silica than other accessions in their stems. □

Inhibitory effects of insecticides on entomogenous fungi *Metarrhizium anisopliae* and *Beauveria bassiana*

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M. anisopliae and *B. bassiana* are the most commonly isolated entomogenous fungi from field-collected brown planthopper (BPH) in the Philippines. Because BPH resurgence is linked with insecticide application, it may be that insecticides applied to control BPH also inhibit natural enemies of BPH. We evaluated the effect of insecticides recommended for BPH control and BPH resurgence-causing insecticides on the germination of *M. anisopliae* and *B. bassiana* spores.

Insecticide was mixed into the culture media before planting, or was surface-applied on hardened media. All insecticides significantly reduced spore germination of both fungi (see table). *M. anisopliae* was more sensitive to insecti-